

Thioamides and Thioureas in Organic Synthesis

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THE title functionals, $-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{S})-$ and $-\text{NH}-\text{C}(=\text{S})-\text{NH}-$ possess three and four reactive sites respectively and constitute versatile starting materials for condensation with a variety of reagents for procuring various sized heterocyclic rings.¹⁻³ Due to the presence of two or more nucleophilic sites, their reactions with biselectrophilic reagents give heterocycles possessing one or more of these heteroatoms.¹⁻³ Many of the thiourea and thioamide derivatives react with nucleophilic reagents. For instance, N-ethoxycarbonyl thioamides react with binucleophiles depending upon the relative positions of the two nucleophilic sites in the reagents. When the nucleophilic groups are attached to each other or are present on the same carbon atom, the reactions occur at the thiocarbonyl and the carbonyl carbon atoms with the elimination of H_2S and EtOH and form five (I) and six membered heterocycles respectively. With 1,2, 1,3, or 1,4 binucleophiles, the reactions proceed at the thiocarbonyl carbon with the elimination of H_2S and ethyl carbamate to provide five, six or seven membered heterocycles (II, $n=1, 2, 3$) and consequently one carbon fragment of the thioamide is transferred in between two nucleophilic sites of such reagents.^{1,b}

SCHEME 1

Recently, the chemistry of these moieties has developed rather rapidly in other directions mainly because of the fact that these moieties when present in acyclic systems or embedded in cyclic systems affect the nature and thus reactions at their own or nearby carbon nuclei. Secondly, these structural units undergo cleavage reactions under a variety of conditions. Such sequences of chemical operations have provided new reactions for the synthesis of various categories of organic compounds⁴. Corey's⁵ synthesis of aldehydes using benzothiazole (III) containing an embedded thioamide unit elaborates one such use. Here, it has been shown that anions can be formed on the aromatic nucleus itself or on the α -carbon and that these anions add easily to carbonyl compounds. Appropriate bond formation reactions run on these attached units followed by sodium borohydride reduction and acid catalysed hydrolytic cleavage furnish homologated and variously

substituted aldehydes and even Robinson annelation products⁵.

SCHEME 2

During the past five years, we have been interested in the use of thioamides and thioureas, both for the syntheses of heterocycles and other categories of organic compounds. For the Basudev Banerjee memorial lecture (1977), this work alongwith relevant works of contemporary workers shall be presented.

Hantzsch synthesis, involving the acid catalysed condensations of biprotic and monoprotic thioamides with α -haloketones is a widely used method for the synthesis of thiazoles and thiazolium salts. In this manner, a synthesis of thiaza [ring C] steroid skeleton was projected through the condensations of isoquinoline-1(2H)-thione and quinazoline-4(3H)-thione with α or β -haloketones. Using α -chlorocyclohexanone, the intermediates: 1-[(α -oxocyclohexyl)thio]isoquinoline and

* Basudev Banerjee Memorial Lecture, 1977, delivered at the Annual Convention of Chemists, 1978, held at Andhra University, Waltair, on December 28, 1978.

4-[(α -oxocyclohexyl)thio]quinazoline formed under basic conditions could be cyclodehydrated with acids to provide 8, 9, 10, 11-tetrahydrobenzothiazolo[2, 3-a]isoquinolinium salt (IV, X=CH): and 8-aza-11-thia-C-nor-D-homo-steroid skeleton⁷ and 8,9,10,11-tetrahydrobenzothiazolo[3,2-c]quinazolin-7-ium salt (IV, X=N): a 6, 8-diaza-11-thia-C-nor-D-homo-steroid skeleton⁸. Likewise, N-[(1-isoquinolinylthio)methyl] succinimide obtained from sodium isoquinolinylthiolate-1 and N-bromomethyl succinimide provides 1,2-dihydro-1-oxo-12H-pyrrolo [2', 1' : 4, 5] [1, 3, 5] thiadiazino [2, 3-a] isoquinolin-4-ium salt (V) and 8, 13-diaza-11-thia-steroid skeleton⁹.

SCHEME 3

As a modification of the Hantzsch synthesis, the carbonium ion generated from appropriately placed double bond has been sought to work as the electrophilic site in place of the carbonyl carbon, for attack of the thioamide N, to form the thiazole ring. Thus 1-allylthioisoquinoline and 1-[(α -cyclohexenyl)thio] isoquinoline cyclise to 3-methyl-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2, 3-a] isoquinolinium salt (VI)¹⁰ and 7a, 8, 9, 10, 11, 11a-hexahydrobenzothiazolo[2,3-a]isoquinolinium salt(VII)⁷.

SCHEME 4

Reductive modifications of these fused thiazolium salts have not been much fruitful. The complex metal hydride reductions of the tricyclic system (VI)¹⁰ proceed smoothly to form (VIII) and (IX) but in the case of the tetracyclic systems, (IV, V, VII), cleavage reactions prevail^{7,8,9} and sodium borohydride reduction of (IV, X=N) forms (X) and (XI) which are formed equally well in the reactions of (IV, X=N) with water or aqueous sodium hydroxide¹¹. Evidently the attack of the hydroxide ion at C_{12a} of (IV, X=N) resulting in the displacement of S and at C₈ resulting in ring opening and its extrusion, have taken place. Such hydrolytic S-C₂ and N-C₂ bond cleavages in thiazolium¹² and quinazoline¹³ rings are well documented. But in the case of the reaction of aq. sodium hydroxide with (VI),

a dihydrothiazolium derivative, in addition to 2-(2-mercapto-1-methylethyl)-1(2H)-isoquinolone (XII), formed by thiazolium S-C₂ (S-C_{10b} in case of VI) bond cleavage¹², thiazolium ring N-C₄ (C₂-N in case of VI) cleavage has taken place to form 1-[(1,2-dihydro-1-isoquinolyl)thio]-2-propanone (XIII)¹⁴. This mode of the latter reaction has been postulated through the C₈→C_{10b} hydride shift in (VI) forming a stable tertiary carbonium ion at C₈ followed by the attack of the hydroxide ion and ring cleavage. Chemical and physical (cmr) evidences supporting such a hydride shift have been provided¹⁴.

SCHEME 5

In the sodium ethoxide catalysed condensations of α -chlorocyclohexanone with isoquinoline-2(H)-thione and quinazoline-4(3H)-thione, performed in DMF at elevated temperature or for longer periods, 1-(α -oxocyclohexyl)-isoquinoline (XVII, X=CH) and 4-(α -oxocyclohexyl)quinazoline (XVII, X=N) are formed by sulphur extrusion of the thioamide derivatives: 1-[(α -oxocyclohexyl)thio] isoquinoline (XV, X=CH) and 4-[(α -oxocyclohexyl)thio] quinazoline (XV, X=N). Since the two carbon atoms of the heterocyclic and cyclohexanone moieties linked in these products (XVII), are intercepted by sulphur atom in their precursors (XIV), the sulphur extrusion has proceeded via the thiiran intermediate(XVI) formed by the electrocyclic closure of the potential thiocarbonyl ylid(XV) generated as a result of the deprotonation of the active methylene group in (XIV)¹⁵.

Such a base catalysed desulphurisation was first reported by Knott¹⁶ and 2-phenacylthio-3-methyl benzothiazolium salt(XVIII) was converted to 2-phenacyl-

SCHEME 6

cyclidene-3-methylbenzothiazole (XIX), evidently through thiocarbonyl ylid and thiiran intermediates. The intermediacy of such species in related sulphur extrusion reactions has been well established both by physical means¹⁷ and chemically by trapping the ylids with active dipolarophiles¹⁸.

SCHEME 7

In a broader synthetic perspective, these sulphur extrusion reactions should proceed equally well with thioamide derivatives of the type, (XIV), possessing other anion stabilising groups. Thus, the sequence of reactions depicted in scheme 8, would provide a facile synthesis of bifunctional organic intermediates (XX), which are widely used in the synthesis of heterocycles. Compounds of the type (XX), have in the past been obtained by Bischler Napieralski cyclisation¹⁹ and recently Wittig reaction has also been applied to amides²⁰ and thioamides²¹ for procuring such compounds.

SCHEME 8

This projected sulphur extrusion in thioamide and thiourea derivatives possessing appropriately placed anion stabilising groups (-CO-, >C=N-) has also been performed with the help of triphenyl phosphine. Eschenmosher²² desulphurised (XXI) to (XXII) and Heff²³ obtained (XXIV) from (XXIII). Eschenmosher

further employed this sulphur extrusion reaction in the synthesis of B/C component of corrins²⁴.

SCHEME 9

Now sodium ethoxide catalysed sulphur extrusions in DMF solution have been studied with thioamide derivatives: [α -(quinazolin-4-yl-thio)] ketones, esters and nitrile and corresponding α -[quinazolin-4-(3H)-ylidene] ketones, esters and nitrile^{25,26} are formed. α -(Quinazolin-4-ylthio) ketones and esters, (XXV) and (XXVI) are obtained by the nucleophilic substitution reactions of corresponding α -halogenoketones and esters with quinazolin-4-thiolate in ethanol solution. A similar

SCHEME 10

displacement in chloroacetonitrile forms 2-imino-2, 3-dihydrothiazolo[2, 3-a] quinazolinylium chloride (XXVII) but in DMF solution, (quinazolin-4-ylthio)acetonitrile (XXVIII) is formed. Compounds, (XXV) and (XXVIII), which have no additional α -substituent, on stirring in DMF containing an equivalent amount of sodium ethoxide, give the corresponding α -[quinazolin-4(3H) ylidene] ketones, esters (XXIX) and nitrile (XXX). The ketones and esters (XXVI) which bear an α -methyl group, under similar conditions, give (XXXI) which possess exocyclic single bond rather than double bond. This behaviour of alpha-substituted ketones and esters is ascribed to steric hindrance by the α -substituent in accommodating the planar exocyclic bond system. Thus the structure of the tautomeric product depends upon the presence or absence of α -substituent in α -halogenoketones and esters used. This reaction also proceeds in ethanol-sodium ethoxide. However, in the case of (XXV, R=OEt), and (XXVI, R=OEt), here, the nucleophilic substitution prevails and 4-ethoxyquinazoline is formed along with the corresponding α -mercaptoester. This observation provides a synthesis of α -mercaptoesters which have recently been synthesised, likewise, by nucleophilic displacement of the side chain in pyridinium derivatives (XXXII) with hydroxide ion²⁷.

A comparison of the desulphurisation of α -(pyrrolidin-2-ylthio) propanone and (XXV, R=Ph) with (i) triphenyl phosphine²² and (ii) DMF-sodium ethoxide²⁵ shows that with the former reagent, the reaction takes much longer time and the products can only be isolated after chromatography of the product mixture, which also contains triphenylphosphine sulphide and triphenylphosphine oxide. Thus, DMF-sodium ethoxide, where applicable, is a more effective reagent for desulphurisation of such carbothioamide derivatives and its use offers the practical advantage of isolation of the desulphurised products by crystallisation.

Ethyl bromocynoacetate and thioureas give 2-(substituted amino)-4-amino-5-carbomethoxythiazole derivatives²⁸ but thioacetamide and ethyl bromocynoacetate, under similar conditions is reported to behave anomalously²⁹ and form elemental sulphur and polymeric products. A reinvestigation of this reaction indicates that it is another spectacular case of a sulphur extrusion reaction and ethyl α -cyano- β -amino-crotonate (XXXIII, R=CH₃) is formed in good yield³⁰. Since ethyl α -cyano- β -aminoacrylates have been used as intermediates in the synthesis of 4-amino-5-cyanopyrimidines³¹ and have been obtained by the condensations of ethyl cyanoacetate with amidines and iminoethers³¹ in relatively poor yields, a new approach to the synthesis of such acrylates (XXXIII), R = H, C₆H₅, C₆H₅CH₂- etc.) by sulphur extrusion in the condensations of mono and biprotic thioamides with ethyl bromocynoacetate in ethanol or in ethanol containing an equivalent amount of sodium ethoxide, has been developed^{32,33}. In the production of (XXXIII), a C=C bond is formed between the active methylene group of ethyl bromocynoacetate and the electrophilic carbon of the thioamide with the loss of sulphur. Here, again, we suggest, that the adduct (XXXIV) initially formed, is

deprotonated to the corresponding ylid which undergoes electrocyclic closure to the thliaran derivative and the desulphurisation follows^{32,33}.

SCHEME 11

Monoprotic thioamides [thiobenzanilide, pyrrolidin-2(1H)-thione and quinazolin-4(3H)-thione] with ethyl bromocynoacetate under same conditions, similarly, form the unsaturated esters, (XXXIIIa, XXXV and XXXVI, X=N) respectively. Isoquinoline-1-(2H)-thione and pyridine-1-(2H)-thione under identical conditions gave fused thiazolium salts, (XXXVIII) and (XXXIX) but isoquinoline-1 (2H)-thione in DMF containing an excess of sodium ethoxide gives the unsaturated cyanoester (XXXVI, X=CH). These results indicate that in the reactions of thioamides with ethyl bromocynoacetate, after the formation of the intermediates of the type (XXXVII), there are two competing pathways: a, episulphide ring formation followed by extrusion of sulphur and b, formation of the thiazole ring by attack of the nitrogen of the thioamide at the C≡N group as depicted in (XXXVII). In the case of isoquinoline-1(2H)-thione and pyridine-2 (1H)-thione, mode b prevails because of the presence of a suitably placed nucleophilic nitrogen atom and aromatic stability of the products (XXXVIII)

SCHEME 12

and (XXXIX). In the case of quinazoline-4(3H)-thione, the nitrogen atom of the thioamide unit is less nucleophilic and in (XXXVII, X=N) mode *a* prevails. In the case of pyrrolidine-2(1H)-thione, the expected thiazolium salt to be formed via mode *b* lacks aromatic stabilisation and hence mode *a* is followed. In the presence of an excess of the base, in the highly polar medium, in the case of isoquinoline-1(2H)-thione, the generation of an anion at the active methylene group of the intermediate, (XXXVII, X=CH), facilitates mode *a* and thereby desulphurisation to (XXXVI, X=CH). Thus, these reactions provide a single step method for the incorporation of a cyano (ethoxycarbonyl) methylene moiety at thioamide carbon³³.

In the reactions of ethyl bromomalonate with monoprotic thioamides-[isoquinoline-1(2H)-thione and quinazoline-4(3H)-thione] in DMF, in the presence of sodium ethoxide, the intermediates, (XL, X=CH, N) instantaneously convert to the mesoions: 2-carboxy-3-hydroxythiazolo [2, 3-a] isoquinolinium (XLI, X=CH) and quinazolinium (XLI, X=N) hydroxide inner salts³⁴. Here, evidently, (XL), due to the lower acidity of the active methylene group of the ethyl malonate moiety do not undergo deprotonation and alternately, the thiazole ring formation to provide stabilized aromatic mesoions (XLI) takes place. Potts has recently reported alternate synthesis of such 4-hydroxythiazolium hydroxide inner salts which undergo additions with active olefins and alkynes and the adducts lose H₂S and sulphur respectively to provide a synthesis of 2-pyridones³⁵. Barton has transformed these mesoions photochemically in the presence of tributylphosphine to β-lactams³⁶.

SCHEME 13

In the case of a monoprotic thioamide, pyrrolidine-2(1H)-thione, the base catalysed condensation of ethyl bromomalonate gives sulphur extrusion product (XLII)⁴¹. This observation has been ascribed to the lack of aromatic stabilisation of the mesoion expected to be formed in this case. Likewise, Barton³⁶ has obtained (XLIII).

SCHEME 14

In qualitative analysis, thioacetamide, a biprotic thioamide has been developed as an alternative reagent to hydrogen sulphide gas for precipitating soft metal ions as their sulphides³⁷. The reactions leading to this precipitation which involves the transfer of sulphur from the thioamide to the metal ions depends upon pH and upon the metal ion. Earlier, these reactions had been studied under heterogeneous conditions. Recently, the mechanisms (scheme 14) of these reactions have been studied under homogeneous conditions and along with metal sulphides, organic nitriles corresponding to the thioamides used, have been isolated³⁸.

SCHEME 15

We have found that biprotic thioamides with α or β-haloketones, esters or nitriles in aq. sodium hydroxide medium form the symmetrical functionalised (corresponding to the halide used) organic sulphides (XLVII)^{39,40}. These reactions, evidently proceed by the mechanism depicted in scheme 16 which is supported by the

SCHEME 16

isolation of the intermediate (XLVI) in one case and the formation of carboxylic acids and ammonia.

When these reactions of thioamides with α -halo-ketones, esters and nitriles are performed under nonhydrolytic conditions viz., DMF-OEt; the conditions which have been used for sulphur extrusion in adducts of type (XLV) obtained from monoprotic thioamides, again, (XLVII) along with the nitriles corresponding to the thioamides are formed⁴¹.

SCHEME 17

Hence, biprotic thioamides serve the same purpose of sulphur transfer as has traditionally been performed by sodium sulphide in the synthesis of organic sulphides from reactive halides. The use of these biprotic thioamides offer following advantages over that of sodium sulphide as sulphur transfer reagents⁴².

1. Thioamides are neither hygroscopic nor sensitive to air as opposed to sodium sulphide and can thus be used stoichiometrically and under anhydrous conditions.

2. Thioamides are soluble in common polar organic solvents and the reactions can be run in non-aqueous media, in the presence of a broad range of bases and solvents. In contrast, the use of sodium sulphide requires the presence of water thereby leading to a two phase system in many organic solvents.

This sulphur transfer technique has now been elegantly used in the synthesis of large ring cyclophanes (XLVIII), involving nucleophilic substitutions at benzylic carbon atoms with sulphur of thioacetamide⁴³. Benzohydrazonyl sulphides have similarly been procured from benzohydrazonyl chlorides and thioamides⁴³.

XLVIII
SCHEME 18

On the other hand, this sulphur transfer reaction, constitutes a specific synthetic approach for the conversion of thioamides to corresponding nitriles which transformation has earlier been reported with the help of (i) dichlorocarbene⁴⁴, (ii) triphenylphosphine, carbontetrachloride, triethylamine⁴⁵, (iii) diethyl azocarboxylate, triphenylphosphine⁴⁶ and bis (triphenylstanyl) carbodiimide⁴⁷. Similarly ketimines⁴⁸ and carbodiimides⁴⁹ have been procured from monoprotic thioamides and disubstituted thioureas.

The enamine character of ethyl β -aminocrotonate was demonstrated by Robinson⁵⁰ and Behrend⁵¹ through their reactions with isothiocyanates (scheme 19). Stevens⁵² exploited the use of ethyl β -aminocrotonates, in condensations with acyl isothiocyanates, for the synthesis of pyrimidine-4(3H)-thione derivatives (XLIX) through the cyclodehydration of the thioamide intermediates (L, $n=0$), formed by the attack of enamine carbon at the isothiocyanato carbon.

SCHEME 19

With the aim of procuring the thioamide intermediates (L, $n=1, 2$ etc.) as precursors for a similar synthesis of medium sized heterocycles, a reaction of 1, 1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl isothiocyanate with ethyl β -aminocrotonate has been studied⁵³. Instead of corresponding (L), here, 4, 6, 6-trimethyl-3, 6-dihydropyrimidine (LIV) is formed alongwith 2-amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-4H-1,3-thiazine (LV). The latter is formed as the major product, when this reaction is run in solvents of higher dielectric constants. This reaction has been visualized to proceed through the intermediate (LI) formed by the interaction of the isothiocyanato carbon and amino nitrogen (scheme 20). (LI) should exist as a mixture of thiol (LIb) and thione (LIa) tautomers. In solvents of higher dielectric constant, such thiourea derivatives are known to exist mainly as thiols (LIb)⁵⁴. Both these tautomers can cyclodehydrate as shown in scheme 20 to provide (LII) and (LIII) which through enamine hydrolysis form (LIV) and (LV) respectively alongwith ethyl acetoacetate. Thus the formation of (LIV) and/or (LV) by the cyclisation of the intermediate thiourea adduct (LI) is determined by its prevailing tautomeric structure which in turn is dependant upon the nature of the solvent used in the reaction. This approach provides a facile synthesis of otherwise difficultly available 2-amino-4H-1,3-thiazines because the reactions of thioureas with α - β -unsaturated ketones give 2-amino-6H-1,3-thiazines alongwith corresponding pyrimidine derivatives of type (LIV)⁵⁵. The structural distinctions of such isomeric aminothiazines and pyrimidine-2-thiones has been conveniently made with the help of PMR and CMR data⁵⁶.

SCHEME 20

Similar reaction of ethyl β-anilinoacrylate and 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl isothiocyanate gives 2-anilino-4,4,6-trimethyl-6H-1,3-thiazine (LVI, R=Ph) and 3-phenyl-4,6,6-trimethyl-3,6-dihydropyrimidine (LVII, R=Ph)⁵⁷. In 1970, Ignatova and coworkers⁵⁸ reported that on heating in conc. HCl, (LVII, R=Ph) rearranges to (LVI, R=Ph). For a comparison of (LVI, R=Ph), we repeated this reaction at 100–110° in an oil bath and

SCHEME 21

observed that the product formed is different from (LVI, R=Ph), obtained by us⁵⁷. It has the structure, 2-anilino-4,4,6,6-trimethyl-6H-1,3-thiazine (LVIII, R=Ph) which has been synthesized by the acid catalysed condensation of mesityl oxide and phenylthiourea⁵⁵.

In the formation of (LVIII, R=Ph), it has been noticed that initially the thiourea derivative (LIX, R=Ph) is formed. This transformation could take place through protonation of (LVII) at enamine C₅ to form the immonium salt (LX) followed by hydrolytic ring cleavage. The intermediate (LIX), as such thermally or after protonation undergoes β-elimination to form mesityl oxide and phenylthiourea which recondense to form (LVIII, R=Ph). Compound (LIX, R=Ph), prepared alternately from 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl isothiocyanate and aniline also forms (LVIII, R=Ph)⁵⁹, by heating in HCl at 100–110°. Russian workers have possibly visualised Dimroth rearrangement⁶⁰ viz., formation of (LIX) and its recyclisation by attack of S on CO. But in our hands, the reaction has evidently followed a different pathway.

4,6,6-Trimethyl-3,6-dihydropyrimidine (LVII, R=H) also undergoes acid catalysed transformation to 4,6,6-trimethyl-6H-1,3-thiazine (LVIII, R=H) and thiourea. Additionally, a dimer of the precursor is also formed⁵⁹.

The dimerisation of enamines under acidic conditions involving carbon-carbon bond formation between the α-electrophilic carbon of one molecule of a protonated enamine with the nucleophilic β-carbon of another molecule of the enamine is well documented⁶¹ (scheme 22).

SCHEME 22

In the compound (LVII, R=H), in addition to the enamine β-carbon atom (C₅), another nucleophilic site is present at the exocyclic thioureido sulphur. Hence, C₄ of (LX, R=H), formed from (LVII, R=H) under acidic conditions, could interact at C₅ of (LVII, R=H) to form both (LXI) and (LXII) or with the sulphur of (LVII, R=H) to furnish (LXIII) (scheme 23). This dimer, therefore, could have the structure (LXI), (LXII) or (LXIII). Its nmr spectrum shows diffused signals which are not of much assistance in structure elucidation. In the mass spectrum, the base peak at m/e 157 for the cation (LX, R=H) supports all these structures equally well. The carbon-13 spectrum shows that of the fourteen carbon atoms, ten are sp³ and four are sp² hybridised.

In the off-resonance proton decoupled spectrum only one sp^2 carbon signal is split into a doublet indicating that it carries a hydrogen atom and the remaining three sp^3 carbons do not bear any hydrogens. On this evidence, therefore, the dimer, has been assigned the structure, 4-[1, 4-dihydro-4, 6, 6-trimethyl-2-pyrimidyl]thio]-tetrahydro-4,6,6-trimethyl-2(1H) pyrimidine thione (LXIII). Its formation from (LVII, R=H) indicates that unlike dimerisation in other enamines where the β -carbon of one enamine molecule interacts at the α -carbon of the other protonated enamine molecule, in this case, the sterically more available nucleophilic site viz., thioureido S, present at one enamine molecule has

attacked the $>C=N^{\oplus}<$ carbon of another protonated enamine molecule, preferably.

SCHEME 23

Zigeuner⁶³ has assigned structure (LXIV) to the dimer obtained similarly but this structure is not favoured by the only one downfield signal for thione, $>C=S^{\delta+}$, carbon atom in the carbon-13 spectrum.

Hence, our studies show that 4,6,6-trimethyl-3,6-dihydro-pyrimidine-2-thiones (LVII, R=Ph, H) react with acids to form thioureas and the corresponding 2-amino-4,6,6-trimethyl-6H-1,3-thiazines (LVIII, R=Ph, H) and not 2-amino-4,4,6-trimethyl-4H-1,3-thiazines (LVI, R=Ph, H) as previously reported. In the case of (LVII, R=H), an additional dimeric product (LXIII) is also obtained. The lack of formation of a dimer in the case of (LVII, R=Ph), may be due to the steric hindrance posed by the phenyl group at N in (LX, R=Ph) towards attack at the adjacent carbon atom by the thioureido S of (LVII, R=Ph).

In the case of compounds (LVII, R=alkyl), under similar conditions, compounds (LVIII, R=alkyl) are formed alongwith the corresponding thioureas. Even compounds (LVIII), under relatively vigorous conditions again decompose to thiourea derivatives. It has also been noticed that these reactions of compounds (LVII) performed at lower temperature but for longer periods also afford (LVI). Compounds (LVII) are structurally related to biological pyrimidines and these pyrimidine to thiazine transformations can be used in the synthesis of modified nucleosides as have some pyrimidine or thiazine transformations performed with the help of nucleophiles, been used⁶⁴.

We have seen that the electrophilic isothiocyanato carbon of 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl isothiocyanate fails to react with enamine carbon of ethyl β -aminocrotonate. These results have been attributed to both the reduced nucleophilicity of the enamine β -carbon due to the presence of ethoxycarbonyl group and the weakened electrophilicity of the isothiocyanato carbon atom due to its insulation from the activating conjugative influence of the carbonyl group. The reactions of 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl-isothiocyanate with cyclohex-1-enyl morpholine, piperidine or pyrrolidine which possess relatively enhanced nucleophilicity at the β -carbon, run by heating the reaction mixtures give the thioamides (LXV) which could be formed from the intermediates (LXVI) by β -elimination of mesityl oxide (scheme 24). On hydrolysis, compounds (LXV) give, 2-oxocyclohexancarbothioamide (LXVII). Hence, this approach affords a means of introducing a thio-carbonyl group at the enamine β -carbon which effectively is the position α to carbonyl group of a ketone. Compound (LXVI, R = pyrrolidine) has been isolated by running the reaction of cyclohex-1-enyl pyrrolidine, a relatively reactive enamine and 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutylisothiocyanate at ambient temperature.

SCHEME 24

Likewise, compounds (LXVIII), on heating also undergo β -elimination to form mesityl oxide and the

carbothioamide derivative of the secondary amine (LXIX). However, Zigeuner⁶⁸ has reported that on heating (i) (LXVIII, N = morpholine) or (ii) a mixture of 1,1-dimethyl-3-oxobutyl-isothiocyanate and morpholine, a pyridine derivative (LXX) is formed. But we have noticed that both these reactions, under the reported conditions, provide morpholine carbothioamide as the major product.

SCHEME 25

Thioureas have extensively been used in the synthesis of fused thiazole containing heterocycles. One such

SCHEME 26

use was made by Narang and coworkers⁶⁷ in the synthesis of thiazoloquinazolones. It was observed that the condensations of *o*-carbomethoxy anilinium thiocyanate (LXXI) with α -haloketones (LXXII) or *o*-carbomethoxyanilinium chloride (LXXIII) with α -thiocyanatoketones (LXXIV) provide only 5*H*-thiazolo [3, 2-*a*] quinazoline-5-ones (LXXV) when R=aryl and both 5*H*-thiazolo [2,3 *b*] quinazoline-5-ones (LXXVI) and (LXXVII) when R = alkyl.

The mode of reaction depicted in (LXXVIII) can give the angular products (LXXV, LXXVII) and the thiourea intermediate (LXXIX) can cyclise to give the products of both angular and linear orientation (LXXVII and LXXVI).

SCHEME 27

The problem of how has the nature of the ketone viz., alkyl or aryl guided the mode of cyclisation of the intermediate thiourea adduct (LXXIX), intrigued us for a long time. Now, it has been found that intermediates of the type (LXXX) are formed in these reactions, evidently by only quinazolone ring formation from (LXXIX). Further, compounds (LXXX) which are aminoketones exhibit a spectacular aminoketone-carbinolamine tautomerism^{69, 69}. Compound (LXXX, R = aryl) exists entirely as a ketone (LXXX)⁶⁹ and (LXXX, R = alkyl) exists as a mixture of two carbinolamines, (LXXXI) and (LXXXII) with the latter as the major constituent. The prevalence of (LXXXII) has been attributed to the steric hindrance posed in the formation of (LXXXI)⁶⁹. The carbinolamine tautomers (LXXXI) and (LXXXII) which are tertiary alcohols dehydrate easily under acidic conditions to give (LXXVII) and (LXXVI) respectively, and have been isolated only under alkaline conditions.

SCHEME 28

In the reactions depicted in (scheme 26), the intermediate (LXXX, R = aryl) could be isolated as under these conditions (LXXX, R = aryl) an aminoketone, does not cyclodehydrate. Whereas, in the case of the reactions of α -haloketones or α -thiocyanato-ketones (LXXII and LXXIV, R = alkyl), the carbinolamines (LXXXI and LXXXII, R = alkyl) are not isolated because these carbinolamines dehydrate instantaneously under the acidic conditions of the reactions.

Hence, in the case of the condensations of (LXXII, R = aryl) and (LXXIV, R = aryl), the only route leading to the formation of thiazoloquinazolones proceeds through (LXXVIII) because the route involving the intermediate (LXXX) stops at this stage and thus the reaction provides only (LXXV) and not (LXXVI). In the case of the condensations of (LXXII and LXXIV, R = alkyl), the route involving the intermediate (LXXX) gives both (LXXVII and LXXVI), through the carbinolamines (LXXXI and LXXXII) and (LXXVII) is additionally formed via (LXXVIII) also. In conclusion, the existence or non-existence of the intermediate (LXXX) as carbinolamine is responsible for the difference in the behaviour of alkyl and aryl ketone derivatives in these thiazole forming reactions.

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